

Assessment of Electronic Voting Technologies in African Context

Shikha Vyas-Doorgapersad

*School of Public Management, Governance and Public Policy, College of Business and Economics
University of Johannesburg, South Africa*

The integrity of holding elections shows the ethical culture of role-players and creates a good image for a country on a global platform. Unethical means employed to gain votes may hamper public trust which is detrimental to the social upliftment in a country context. The article aims to explore the issues of integrity in elections and understand the significance of considering the use of electronic voting technologies (EVTs) to combat corruption and misconduct involved. The study explores the aspect of ethical elections in the context of Africa. The article utilises secondary sources to compile information, hence form part of a qualitative desktop analysis. The information was gathered using literature and document reviews. The conceptual analysis was used to analyse and assess the information. The findings explore that there are various challenges that may occur when votes are not secured ethically. Internally, it impacts peoples' trust in their political representatives, questioning the processes of electoral systems and obligating the representatives not by choice but by fraudulent means of voting arrangements. Externally, at the global level, countries involved in unethical means of securing votes may lose reputation, may face sanctions, and may have a negative impact on economic development, as other countries may withdraw export-import or other forms of economic activities with countries under mistrust. The article offers practical recommendations to implement ethics in the electoral system as a contribution to the study.

Keywords: Africa, electronic voting, integrity, qualitative research

Electronic voting is based on the use of technological or digital devices to perform the relevant task. The voting process uses equipment such as computers available at the election booths to cast votes. However, the process requires the availability of internet or wifi access so electoral personnel can get information regarding registered voters, and votes can be recoded in the EVT system. This arrangement is designed to prevent maladministration, which is a form of poor governance, and may therefore be considered a system that fosters an environment of good governance. However, whether the process is electronic-based or traditional paper-based, it requires competing criteria (refer to Kumar & Begum, 2012:42) to serve the purpose of establishing ethical norms in public administration processes.

International IDEA (2017: 4) adds that electronic voting refers to the use of electronic systems to cast and count votes. Freyer (2017:4) also notes that there are a variety of voting systems such as optical systems and punched cards that are widely known. In addition, there are systems such as direct recording electronic systems (DREs) that are gaining momentum. The article focuses on the electronic voting machines (EVMs) as the focus of the study.

International IDEA (2017:6) clarifies that EVMs are standalone devices without a computer network connection. These machines do not transmit or receive any signal and on that basis, cannot be intercepted. Additionally, these devices without a computer network connection can be powered by batteries, and hence, in regions where there is an electricity crisis, can be used for voting and for counting of votes afterwards.

This arrangement of voting can also be considered as electronic voting (e-voting) as it requires digitalised means to execute the processes. E-voting is a broad term that includes electronic voting methods as well as electronic vote counting. Voter technology can include optical scan voting systems, punched cards, and specialized voting kiosks, such as self-contained DREs (direct-recording electronic voting systems) (IDEA, 2011:6). Additionally, it may entail sending ballots and votes over the Internet, private computer networks, or cellphones. And without using ballots, EVM naturally contributes to complete voting secrecy (IDEA, 2011:6). Additionally, as the IDEA (2011: 6) considers and hence deduced that EVT may promote good governance as it fosters democracy, enhances public trust and confidence in electoral processes, and create an authentic environment related to elections where political governance and processes may be considered efficient in establishing and performing election-based tasks.

This introduction is the first of the paper's five sections. The research methodology is presented in the second part of this article, and the third part of the essay reviews pertinent literature. In the fourth section, the analysis of relevant papers is discussed. It concludes and offers recommendations for enhancement.

Method

The study utilized the qualitative desktop approach to compile information. The constraints of quantitative research methodologies

Author Note

Shikha Vyas-Doorgapersad, Professor, School of Public Management, Governance and Public Policy, College of Business and Economics, University of Johannesburg, South Africa
Orcid Number: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8146-344X>
I have no known conflict of interest to disclose.
Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to Shikha Vyas-Doorgapersad, Professor, School of Public Management, Governance and Public Policy, College of Business and Economics, University of Johannesburg, South Africa
E-mail: svyas-doorgapersad@uj.ac.za

do not apply to qualitative approaches. A much more flexible method is provided by qualitative data, which can be equally important in providing context and possibly explaining something that numbers alone cannot tell if replies don't match the researcher's expectations (Kooiman, 2003:19). To achieve progress, analysts can quickly modify questions, the environment, or any other variable if important information is not being recorded. It enables a researcher to use their intuition or gut feel to determine where useful information will be found to trigger data collection (Kooiman, 2003:19).

Research designs are methods used in research investigations for collecting, analyzing, interpreting, and reporting data. This is the general approach for connecting conceptual research problems to pertinent (& feasible) empirical studies. In other words, the study design determines how the required data will be collected and analyzed, as well as how all of this will help to answer the research question (Grey, 2014:19). When the researcher has little or no historical data to work with, or only a few papers to consult, an exploratory research strategy is used to address the study problem. This research can occasionally be casual and unstructured. It functions as a preliminary research tool that offers a theoretical or hypothetical understanding of the study problem. It won't provide specific answers to the research challenge (Robert, 1997:90). Exploratory research is versatile and provides the first framework for further investigation. It necessitates that the researcher looks at a variety of sources, including disseminated auxiliary data, data from other studies, opinions about the subject, and assumptions about a business, product, or advantage (Robert, 1997:90).

Documents that were accessible in the form of archived files, graphs showing statistics, documents that are available to the public in the form of articles, stories, news, etc., whether in print version or on Google websites. Examples of publicly available materials include government announcements and proceedings, census publications, diaries, institutional memoranda and reports, and other written, visual, and pictorial sources in various formats.

Literature review has four main objectives, which are surveys, syntheses, critically analyses, and present. It integrates and summaries what is known about subject (Newton, 1992:49).

Information was analysed using conceptual analysis. Philosophers are the main users of conceptual analysis when discussing abstract concepts, but all other academic fields greatly benefit from this kind of analysis. Understanding and the growth of knowledge in any field are produced by the belief that a precise definition is first and foremost required in the examination of any idea or concept, before any investigation into its meaning and relationship to other ideas and concepts (Galbraith, 1977:13).

Results

According to De Vries and Bokslag (2016), unchecked human interference has immensely compromised the electoral process, which has resulted in post-electoral contestations and disputes over the integrity and ethical side of the process. To this end, the duo, De Vries and Bokslag (2016: 4) suggest that adoption of such electoral digital technologies has the potential, particularly to improve voting and counting efficiency. This would be one of the major advantages on the basis that past elections have been marred by delays in casting the ballot, with some polling stations even closing before a significant portion of the electorate votes. This is further

compounded by delays in announcement of election results, a challenge believed to be a direct result of cumbersome counting process and method, which remains manual (Chan, 2013; Chan & Gallagher, 2017).

Still on vote casting, Russell and Zamfir (2018: 4) further observe that protections against vote box stuffing, which used to be widespread in rural areas of India when criminals or political activists took over polling places and filled boxes with ballots for a preferred candidate, can be incorporated into electronic voting systems. Since stuffing takes an unreasonably long time, even if the machines end up in the wrong hands, they disclose that voting machines, which are designed to record no more than five votes per minute, have made such operations considerably more difficult (refer to Russell & Zamfir, 2018).

Kersting and Baldershim (2004:3) also concur that digital technologies, especially in elections, promise various advantages. Citing Slaton (2002), Kersting and Baldershim (2004:3) argue that online technology integration could streamline and expedite the election process while lowering expenses. Additionally, vote counting and result presentation could be completed more quickly, precisely, and dependably. Kersting and Baldershim (2004:3) further added that this arrangement has the potential to restore falling rates of interest by members of the public in such democratic practices. In this regard, voter engagement has naturally been a source of hope as declining rates of public participation seen in many Western democracies during the 1980s led to a search for novel approaches to pique voter interest in elections and politics (refer to Kersting & Baldershim, 2004).

Russell and Zamfir (2018: 4) in their listing of benefits borne by EVTs describe tabulation and transmission as the process of transmitting the results of the vote count from polling places to a central polling office, where they are combined to provide the final results (either at the national or constituency level). According to Russel and Zaffir (2018), at least early results can be swiftly published thanks to digital technology, which enables results to be transmitted electronically (for example, via the internet or a mobile phone) and consolidated by a computer. When using paper-based procedures, collecting and computing results from thousands of polling places around the country is frequently the slowest step in the process.

The use of EVTs has great potential in improving many aspects of the electoral process. Goldsmith (2011: 16) indicates that implementation of such technologies particularly increases voter access to the electoral process noting that several populations, such as those who have vision impairments or find it difficult to go to polling places (remote voting), may profit from the increased accessibility offered by these technologies and personnel working from overseas among others. However, it is also advised that the decision to introduce electronic voting and counting systems is complex and thus should not be rushed (Gass, 2011).

Goldsmith (2011: 13) adds that to understand the process of e-voting and counting requires that its adoption be done in a gradual manner, which could sometimes take years rather than months. To cut corners during this deliberation process, a technology that is inappropriate for the election setting may be used, or a choice may be made without the support of important players (IDEA, 2011:6).

Since its inception, the idea of democracy has undergone significant development and is still developing. Therefore, it is not

surprising that ICT has an impact on democratic processes (Krimmer, 2012: 6). Krimmer (2012: 6) further buttresses that since elections are a fundamental democratic activity, this inclusive conversation is particularly crucial when considering the use of ICT in elections. Kersting and Baldersheim (2004: 3) equally observe that high hopes for democracy have resulted from the internet's explosive growth since the 1990s. In light of this, the section below traces the origins and evolution of ICTs in elections often referred to as electronic voting technologies.

Electronic Voting: Understanding the Process

The process of electronic voting is arguably simpler than the traditional paper ballot system although in early stages it might sometimes prove to be complicated (Krimmer et al., 2020:25). However, Shejvali (2014:11) borrowing from the Namibian electronic voting experience, argues that it only takes adequate all stakeholder voter education to inform and educate the voting population about the process of electronic voting and counting. Shejvali (2014) further records that for elections to be successful and democratic, voters must understand their rights and responsibilities, be adequately informed to cast legally valid ballots, and be able to participate in the voting process.

According to Shejvali (2014), in Namibia the transition from the traditional means of voting using a ballot paper which had been practised since Namibia's independence in 1990 to using the EVM, required an enhanced level of voter education, not just in terms of the use of the device but also to ingrain a high level of public trust in the electronic voting system (Shejvali, 2014:16). Thus it can be noted that, before the actual process of voting electronically, there is need for an intensive all stakeholders voter education to equip both electoral officials and stakeholders with relevant skills and also educate the voting public on how to conduct the process and also to increase peoples' confidence and public trust in the novel electoral system.

The electronic voting model of conducting elections is arguably simpler, faster and time conserving and to a relative extent less expensive (Nganje, 2020: 22). The implementation of technology makes the administrative and voting requirements less complex, instead they become simpler and easier to organise (Pratama & Salabi, 2020:12). Thus, the actual process of casting and counting the ballots through EVMs is faster, efficient and preserves resources.

According to Goldsmith (2011: 3), a voter's preference is recorded by an electronic device during electronic voting. A polling station may or may not be the location of the device. However, in cases of remote voting or internet voting, the voting device can be in a remote location. For example, Voters can use a computer to cast their ballot online, or they can utilize a short messaging service (SMS) on their phone. In contrast, electronic counting counts both paper and electronic ballots using an electronic device (Goldsmith, 2011:4). Nonetheless, it should be noted from the beginning that this study is not focusing on remote or internet voting and or electronic counting of paper ballots but is concerned with the utility of electronic voting and counting machines physically located at polling stations.

EVMs created by government-owned equipment manufacturers were introduced in India in the early 2000s. EVMs are a pair of battery-operated devices. One device, the Voting Unit, is used by the voter, and the other, the Control Unit, is operated by an electoral officer. Both devices are connected by a wire. Up to 15 candidates can fit in the voting unit, which has a button for each candidate.

However, up to 4 units can be connected to accommodate up to 60 candidates. Three buttons on the Control Units are used to release a single vote, view the overall number of votes cast, and end the voting process. Until the Close button is pushed, the results button is walled off and concealed (EISA, 2014:4)

Proborno Bulletin (2015) provides an insight into Namibia's e-voting process. According to the Bulletin (2015), in Namibia, A control unit that is coupled to a ballot unit makes up the EVM. By selecting the green button next to their selection on the ballot unit, voters express their support for a specific political party or candidate. A red light next to the green button illuminates when the button is pressed, indicating that the voter's selection has been noted. To finish the voting process, the voter then hits the red "register" button located at the bottom of the unit. The machine is automatically locked when a person casts their ballot. To "open" the machine once more for the following voter, the poll worker needs to press a button on the control unit. Every voter will only be able to cast one ballot thanks to this approach. Thus, locking of the machine by the polling officer prevents double or multiple voting. Proborno Bulletin (2015) further notes that this provision ensures very minimal cases of spoiled votes and reduces the time taken when casting the electronic ballot in comparison with the traditional paper system.

Pratama and Salabi (2020: 24) elaborate that direct recording (DRE) voting machines, which are the commonly used e-voting machines in various electoral systems, notably Brazil, Indonesia, India and Namibia, consist of a keyboard, touch screen or other electronic device to input and save voters' choices automatically. Pratama and Salabi (2020: 24) continue to reveal that the data will then be recapitulated with data from other DRE machines in the data center after the machines have sent the saved data there via the internet, memory card, or printed paper. It can be observed that electronic voting occurs entirely on and through technological software and hardware components. This is a clear indication of the strong link between e-voting and provision of relevant and adequate ICT infrastructure to enable a smooth and easy technological process (Mathe, 2020).

However, Nganje (2020: 3) bemoans the lack of adequate ICT infrastructure in the greater Sub-Saharan Africa. The scholar argues that this impedes a seamless migration from traditional manual voting to digitally enabled electoral processes with potential to transform the electoral landscape and increase public participation in crucial events such as voting (Maphunye, 2020; Mathe, 2020). It should however, be noted that not all of these machines require the existence of complex technology for them to function or be operated. For instance, International IDEA (2017:6) underscores that some Electronic voting machines operate independently and are not linked to any network or computer. In places without electricity, these devices can run entirely on batteries during the voting and counting process because they don't send or receive any signals, making them impenetrable (International IDEA, 2017: 16).

Emergence and Evolution of Electronic Voting Technologies (EVTs)

History of voting or elections is long and predates many civilizations that have occurred in human life. It can be traced back to Ancient Greek, where open or public voting on issues affecting society was common practice (Schwartzberg, 2010). Krimmer (2012) observes that over the centuries, electoral and voting procedures have evolved

from open to secret voting, a phenomenon that has attracted the need to devise technology to deliver this process (of elections). The rapid growth and ubiquity of ICTs has, in turn, had an impact even in democratic processes such as elections (Pratama & Salabi, 2020:12) Pratama and Salabi (2020) also add that mostly during the 19th century, due to the need to assure the secrecy of the voting process or elections, there was a growing need to develop technologies to secure such processes.

During World War II, the concept of utilizing electronic means to allow voters to participate outside of polling places was already developed (Krimmer, 2012:23). However, significantly remarkable developments in electronic voting were made in the 1960s when the United States of America put on trial the first electronic voting machines to be used in an election. Although America does not use an automated or fully electronic system of elections, it is one of the pioneers of this concept whose aim was to ensure efficiency, transparency and eradicate fraud in elections (Krimmer, 2011). To date, 90 % of America's ballots are counted electronically in line with the need to increase accuracy, transparency and efficiency of the electoral process (Fin24, 2019).

McKay et al. (1974) in Krimmer (2012:22) attributes numerous developments in electronic voting to the 20th century where most technological inventions were created. According to Krimmer (2012), the most popular EVM, the direct recording DRE machine was first invented in the US in 1974 and was used in that year in a legally binding election in one of the American states. Jones and Simons (2012) also in Krimmer (2012) argue that the invention of this machine was mainly motivated by the need to reduce time taken in casting a vote and also to make the process more efficient and accurate.

This invention paved the way for developments of the DRE machine in various parts of the world such as Europe, South America and Asia (Alvarez & Hall, 2008). India started to use them in 1999 (Independent Elections Commission 2012). According to Krimmer (2012:23), both of these nations currently employ electronic voting machines (EVMs) nationwide and assert that the technology used for voting and counting allows them to produce voting results more quickly.

In Brazil, Silva (2020: 349) traces the history of electronic voting to the 1930s, where voting machine use was already regulated under the first Brazilian Electoral Code (Law) in 1932 until 1996, when the Electoral Court formally adopted this innovation.

Silva (2020) notes that the e-voting system is the outcome of concepts and prototypes produced throughout the first half of the twentieth century. It should be noted that radio operator Raymundo da Silva created a device that could record total and calculate votes in the 1940s. The current telephone and television sets served as the inspiration for his invention, Televoto. Theoretically, this device may take the place of voting boxes and paper, ensuring speedy vote counting and vote confidentiality (Silva, 2020: 350). Receiving the votes and transferring them to the totalization via circuits and electromagnets would be their procedure. The candidates would then be identified by their names, numbers, and photographs, and the votes would be validated after the voter dialed the legend's and the candidate's numbers (Silva, 2020: 350).

Debnath, Kapoor, and Ravi (2017: 6) record that, in India, the first EVMs were used in 1998 as an experiment in a by-election in Paravul in the state of Kerala. The trio argues that since then, the use of EVMs IN India has evolved resulting in e-voting being the

primary system of voting in the national elections. According to Debnath et al. (2017), by eliminating the need to print millions of ballots, the ECI was able to streamline the voting process, expedite the process of determining results, and lower election expenses. These factors led to the adoption of electronic polling methods. Incorrect and numerous stamps on paper ballots left the voter's selection ambiguous, which ultimately resulted in her vote being disregarded. There was essentially no chance of votes being rejected because EVMs could only record one response.

The adoption of e-voting systems since the 19th century through to the last half of the 20th century has seen countries like Estonia in the 21st century also playing a leading role in the utility of EVTs in the entire conduction of elections (Russel & Zamfir, 2018: 8). Russell and Zamfir (2018: 8) add that the Estonian case presents a rapid evolution of electronic voting as the country has even harnessed the opportunities presented by the internet in the conduction of elections, and argue that Estonia demonstrates the possibility of enhanced electronic voting through the usage of a fairly unusual concept known as i-voting.

The current changes in the traditional voting systems which are gradually being replaced by electronic means or digital application of voting has also been experienced in Sub-Saharan Africa with Namibia providing a case in the country's 2014 and 2019 General Elections. Shejavali (2014: 1) commented in an Elections publication called Election Watch that the Electoral Commission of Namibia decided to use electronic voting machines (EVMs) in a national election at the end of November 2014, making it the first African nation to do so. The decision was made in 2004, when multiple batches of EVMs were purchased from the Indian company Bharat Technologies.

Russel and Zaffir (2018:7) note that Namibia continues to use Indian manufactured EVMs because of their "simple and robust" design. They also indicate that these machines are suitable for conditions mostly prevalent in the developing world such as erratic power supply, limited internet connectivity, poor state of roads and other logistical infrastructure. Thus, one can note that electronic voting has evolved over time resulting in manufacturing of voting machines which suit any environment. As highlighted above, it can also be observed that since the emergence of this concept, various innovations have been made leading to even manufacturing of EVMs that can cater to conditions prevalent in the developing world, particularly Sub-Saharan Africa.

Discussion

Elections, especially in Africa and to a considerable extent so-called mature and developed democracies in Europe and North America, continue to be a highly contested process which in numerous cases has resulted in incomplete or disputed outcomes (Freyer, 2017: 6). Most of these challenges have largely been attributed to the current traditional method of elections, which is predominantly manual in operation. In this respect, De Vries and Bokslag (2016: 2) argue that paper ballots are still used in the majority of countries, and they are tallied by hand after the voting period is over. This has two apparent disadvantages: it wastes paper, it takes time, and it may be more prone to errors than automated vote counting. De Vries and Bokslag (2016: 2) further state that manual voting renders election officials unmeasured access to manipulate the process for a contesting party of their choice.

Commenting about the Brazilian case, Silva (2020:352) submits that to prevent election fraud in Brazil, the SEC recognized that it would be beneficial to limit human intervention in the electoral process. The Electoral Legislation Reform Commission, also known as the Commission of Notables, was established by the SEC in 1995 to oversee the computerization of the voting process. It was made up of judges from the REC, experts, and computer scientists who were tasked with reformulating the laws pertaining to the election process and developing a final electronic voting solution for both majority and proportional elections (Silva, 2020:352).

Meanwhile, Zimbabwe has recorded numerous cases of disputed electoral outcomes as a result of suspected irregularities in the traditional voting and counting processes. This was also evidenced in the Constitutional court challenge by the MDC-Alliance seeking to reverse the electoral outcome that declared Emmerson Mnangagwa of ZANU PF the winner in the 2018 harmonised elections (The Guardian Newspaper, 24 August 2018). The adoption of a biometric voter registration (BVR) seeking to ease and allay concerns over the voter registration process was one of the developments aimed at improving the country's electoral integrity (Maphunye, 2019; Chikwawawa, 2018). Henceforth, one of the major benefits of incorporating EVT in the electoral processes, especially in Zimbabwe, is its potential to improve the counting and publication of results which has a crucial bearing on integrity and legitimacy issues which have remained unresolved in the country's four decades of universal suffrage.

Achieng and Ruhode (2013:9) posit that there is ample evidence of the benefits of election-related technologies. In one study on the usage of election-related technology in South Africa, for example, they disclose that participants preferred electronic voting machines (EVT) over the current paper-based system due to the ease of access, time savings, transportation costs, and the effort required to cast a ballot. Blanc (2007:12) comments that electronic voting technologies play a crucial role in delivering an efficient electoral process. According to Blanc (2007: 12), one of the major advantages of mechanical voting systems, DRE systems and optical scan voting machines, which are examples of electronic voting technologies, is their ability to enhance the vote counting and tabulation, making them faster and more accurate.

On the same token, Blanc (2007: 12) emphasises that while hand-counted ballots can be used in any election, these two methods can be expensive, time-consuming, and prone to errors, making digital and mechanical voting systems more appealing. This is one of the most delicate and significant phases of the electoral process. Thus, one can note that, especially in contexts where disputes have characterised the outcome of electoral processes, as noted in Zimbabwe, it will be advisable to consider incorporating such technologies to ensure credible and efficient voting and counting systems.

The importance of ensuring a correctly and accurately counted vote cannot be over-emphasised. This has been a source of dispute which, in some polities, has degenerated to post-political violence and in others to civil wars (Gyekye-Jandoh, 2014: 187). The scholar argues that in most elections in Africa, accusations of inflation of votes for certain candidates are very common and have led to inconclusive elections, ushering into office governments facing a legitimacy crisis. Gyekye-Jandoh (2014: 187) uses the example of the outcome of the Kenyan elections in 2007, where opposition leader Railah Odinga, after polling 44.1 % against the incumbent, Mwai Kibaki's 46.4% felt the negligible margin had been a result of a

manipulated counting process.

Citing Debrah (2008:4), Gyekye-Jandoh (2014) 187 reveals that Odinga charged that about 300 000 votes had been falsely attributed to Kibaki in most remote constituencies and that the counting process had been manipulated resulting in a rigged electoral outcome. Gyekye-Jandoh (2014: 187) raises another electoral dispute attributed to counting and tabulation errors in Zimbabwe's 2008 harmonised elections. According to Gyekye-Jandoh (2014: 188), this dispute also witnessed a month-long delay in the announcement of results, which further compounded suspicion of tampering with ballots in the counting phase of the election. What is thus common in both cases raised by Gyekye-Jandoh (2014) is the violence that ensued thereafter as a result of a flawed and compromised voting and counting process.

To remedy such electoral challenges and disputes, Blanc (2007:13) argues that one of the major contributions and advantages brought by electronic voting technologies is the ability to prevent voter fraud and ease the voting process. Blanc (2007) generally observes that preventing such irregularities has the potential to forestall incidences of political and electoral violence, as noted in the above highlighted cases. Blanc (2007:15) also highlights that in countries such as Brazil and India, where usage of such technologies is very common, there has been confirmation of their ability to prevent fraud such as ballot counting manipulation and disappearance of ballot boxes.

Russell and Zamfir (2018: 3) concur that vote counting is made faster by technology. Voting machine results in India, which used to take days for paper votes, are counted in two to three hours per constituency, including the time required for checks. Additionally, it saves money by hiring fewer poll workers and lessens the possibility of human error (Russell & Zamfir, 2018: 3). Thus, digital technologies contribute immensely in ensuring an efficient election with counting and tabulation processes that are accurate and not easily prone to error, especially human-induced error.

Russell and Zamfir (2018: 3) also submit that EVTs provide several advantages over conventional paper-based processes at every stage of the election process, from voter registration to ballot counting. On voter registration, Russell and Zamfir (2018:4) state that noting that the challenge of updating and cross-checking paper-based electoral rolls increases the possibility of including deceased voters or numerous entries of the same individual, opening the door for electoral fraud, digital technology significantly streamlines the process of producing registers.

Voter registration process and management of the voter register have been sources of dispute in many electoral contexts with allegations of multiple voting, manipulation and electoral fraud emanating from that process. In some cases, with Zimbabwe being no exception (pre-BVR adoption, the manual process of voter registration and the voter's roll have at some intervals been described as 'shambolic' (ZESN, 2013). The 'shambolic' and 'opaque' process has in many instances been suspected to be deliberate to facilitate easy manipulation and voter fraud (Hove & Harris, 2015:12).

The above sentiment is also shared by Ndlovu-Gatsheni (2012:10) who argues that previous elections in Zimbabwe have witnessed the deployment of a voter roll which was in shambles and outdated in order to enable vote rigging to take place. Many people can register more than once because of the absence of a trustworthy way to verify their identity; in the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC), more than 700,000 people (1 percent of the population) were

found to have done so before the 2011 elections. 45 nations—mostly in Africa—use fingerprint scanning to stop this. Ironically, due to a lack of trustworthy identity credentials and population registries, some of the world's least developed nations have emerged as leaders in the use of biometric technologies in elections (Russell & Zamfir, 2018). This submission confirms the possibility even for least developed countries, especially in Sub-Saharan Africa to adopt EVTs to maintain and even improve integrity and credibility of elections.

In vote casting, Russell and Zamfir (2018: 4) argue that voting issues related to illiteracy can be effectively mitigated with EVMs. They claim that because illiterate voters are unable to read ballots or marking instructions, the number of invalid votes rises. In India, for instance, where 31% of adults lack literacy, many ballots were previously thrown out because of errors like marking the ballot incorrectly or more than once; in numerous elections, the number of discarded votes exceeded the margin of victory, raising questions about the validity of the outcome (Russell & Zamfir, 2018: 4). This issue has been resolved by the introduction of user-friendly electronic voting machines in 2003; voters now simply need to press a button adjacent to the appropriate party logo, which is heavily promoted throughout election campaigns. The scanner can be configured to only accept properly completed votes in systems where voters fill out paper ballots and scan them instead of pressing a button on a computer (Russell & Zamfir, 2018: 4).

Achieng and Ruhode (2013: 3) contribute that e-voting enhances rapid and a more accurate process of voting and counting the votes as the technologies used provide high speed and accuracy as compared to manual traditional systems of casting the vote. This observation is compounded by the submission made by Chikwawawa (2018) that in Zimbabwe, long queues on the Election Day and delays in counting have contributed to diminishing interest amongst voters since in some cases voting can take the whole day (ZESN, 2018). This, in turn, contributes towards high levels of voter apathy especially among young voters in urban areas. On this note, Achieng and Ruhode (2013: 5) observe that Xenakis and Macintosh (2005) submit that electronic voting can greatly enhance the voting process by increasing low turnout among young people who might not be satisfied with the traditional paper-based voting technique. Mathe (2020: 129) commenting about the BVR in African countries, also remarked that such technologies enhance citizens' faith and trust in the electoral process and would increase their interest in the vote.

Conclusion

The article proposes the need to instill an ethical culture in government processes. In this regard, it is suggested that political parties need to have internal policies on ethics and abide by ethical norms of political dealings. The policies obligate government ministries and departments to ensure adherence to ethical values of the government-based processes. In this article, government processes are linked to electoral processes. The institution and people responsible for electoral processes need to undergo ethical training to understand the consequences of misconduct in the affairs of voting system. There needs to be control mechanisms in place to ensure good governance is maintained in election processes. Processes to monitor, evaluate, report and punish the personnel involved in electoral misconduct require critical attention, in Africa and at the global level, holistically.

The purpose of the article is to explain the importance of

electronic voting systems in maintaining the integrity and ethics of electoral procedures. It is believed that interviewing is a basic and necessary step in raising the standard of research. To really make an influence in this fascinating and constantly changing sector, it is crucial to carry out a long-term, thorough study that covers every facet of public administration and government.

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Received September 19, 2025

Revision received October 6, 2025

Accepted October 9, 2025